

varieties became necrotic after 12 d.

The rate of multiplication was consistently higher in the susceptible than in the resistant variety. It appeared that lesion size was not necessarily determined by the population of the pathogen but by a particular host-pathogen relationship. □

Multiplication and development of lesions caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* in diseased rice plants, India.

Days after inoculation	Bacterial cells/cm ² leaf area		Nature and range of lesion length (cm)	
	TN1	ET4141	TN1	IET4141
3	2.83 × 10 ³	1.0 × 10 ³	0.2-0.5, grey green	No lesion
6	2.65 × 10 ⁵	1.5 × 10 ⁴	0.5-1.5, yellow	No lesion
9	2.16 × 10 ³	1.5 × 10 ⁶	2.0-5.0, yellow	0.5-0.8, light yellow
12	2.65 × 10 ⁶	1.33 × 10 ⁵	5.0-10.0, brownish	1.0-1.5, yellow
15	Necrotic lesion	Necrotic lesion	7.0-15.0, straw color	1.5-3.5, brownish

Occurrence of rice ragged stunt virus (RSV) in Sri Lanka

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Plants showing symptoms similar to those of rice RSV were first observed in Hambantota district in 1984. Varieties BG276-5, BG34-8, BG94-1,

BG34-6, and BG380 were affected. Disease incidence ranged from 20 to 70% in farmers' fields in Weeraketiya and Ranna.

Plants with typical symptoms collected from Weeraketiya, Walasmulla, Belliatta, Ranna, and Jandura were tested for virus recovery. Virus-free *Nilaparvata lugens* and *Nephotettix* sp. reared on TN1 plants in insect-proof cages were allowed to

feed on infected plants for 4 d, then confined with 7-d-old TN1 seedlings for 4 d.

The first symptoms similar to those reported for RSV were observed 21 d after inoculation. *N. lugens* but not *Nephotettix* sp. transmitted the disease to TN1 seedlings. Dried infected TN1 leaves were serologically tested at IRRI. ELISA test confirmed RSV in extracts of the leaves. □

Pest Control and Management
INSECTS

Meadow grasshopper
***Conocephalus longipennis* damage to rice spikelets**

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Tettigoniids as foliage feeders occur on rice worldwide. The nocturnal *C. longipennis* (de Haan) is more abundant in crops past the vegetative stage.

It shows dual food habits - as a pest feeding on rice foliage and as a predator of rice bug and stem borer eggs and nymphs of leafhoppers and planthoppers. *Conocephalus* also eats the highly nutritive rice anthers by cutting through the lemma or palea. In the process, it damages rice spikelets.

Whitish cut holes on damaged 1-d-old spikelets become noticeable when they turn brown on the third day (see figure). We found that caged adults can destroy 10-28 spikelets daily.

Conocephalus damage can be distinguished from bird, rat, or rice bug damage because only small holes

Conocephalus damage to rice spikelets: undamaged (left), 1-d-old damage (middle), and 3-d-old damage (right).

are eaten in each spikelet. Feeding birds and rats strip off many spikelets.

Bugs feeding on seeds do not make noticeable holes in spikelets. □